

FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *ARGYRIA SPECIOSA*, SWEET (N.O. CONVULVULACEAE)

BY G. M. KELKAR, N. L. PRALINIKAR AND B. V. BHIDE

The seeds of *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet (N. O. Convolvulaceae) give a fatty oil which has been found to contain the glycerides of palmitic acid (6.78%), stearic acid (29.12%), behenic acid (8.04%), linolenic acid (6.09%), linolic acid (18.17%) and oleic acid. (83.29%).

Argyria speciosa, Sweet (N.O. Convolvulaceae), commonly known as elephant creeper, is abundant throughout India and is often cultivated in Java. It is known by the following names in different Indian languages : Samudra Patra (Sanskrit), Samudraka Pat (Hindi), Samudra Shosh (Gujarathi), Gaguli (Bengalee) and Samudra Shoka (Marathi). It is a large climber, having stout stems and broad round leaves and violet flowers like bells. The seeds have three sides of which one is convex and the other two plane. They are produced four together in a single capsular fruit. They are black when mature.

The roots of this creeper are bitter and are used as an alternative tonic. They are also useful in rheumatic affections and diseases of the nervous systems. In some parts of southern India, the tuber is used in the form of a paste for external application in abscess. The seeds along with the seeds of *Hygrophila spinosa*, T. Anders (N.O. Acanthaceae) are used as a tonic (cf. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. III, p.1707).

The seeds are extracted with different solvents. The petroleum ether extract gives a fatty oil, while all other extracts are yellowish gums.

The seeds contain 10.68% of a fatty oil of a pale yellow colour which does not contain nitrogen and sulphur. The oil on being hydrolysed the free fatty acids are separated into solid and liquid acids by Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method. The liquid acids have been examined and found to contain linolenic acid (10.7%), linolic acid (81.6%) and oleic acid (57.7%).

The liquid acids have a mean molecular weight of 290.8 which suggests that they may contain a high molecular weight acid. The methyl esters of liquid acids have been prepared and fractionally distilled in order to isolate the high molecular weight acid, if present. The different fractions give high molecular weights and varying iodine values which indicate the absence of any high molecular weight acid. The high molecular weight of the mixed liquid acids may be due to the polymerisation of linolenic acid and linolic acid present (cf. Govindrajau, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 14A, 616).

The solid acids have been converted into methyl esters, fractionally distilled, and different fractions hydrolysed and the mixtures of acids obtained are separated

into individual acids by fractional precipitation of their magnesium salts. Individual acids, thus separated, have been identified by their equivalent weights, melting points and mixed melting points with authentic specimens.

The free fatty acids of the oil have the following composition : palmitic acid, 6.73% ; stearic acid, 29.12% ; behenic acid, 6.64% ; linolenic acid, 6.09% ; linolic acid, 18.17% and oleic acid, 33.23%.

The unsaponifiable matter from alcohol is obtained in a crystalline condition (m.p. 129-30°) and gave all the colour reactions of phytosterols.

EXPERIMENTAL

Physical and Chemical Constants of the Oil.—The oil obtained by ether extraction from the seeds had the following constants.

TABLE I

1. Density at 30° ...	0.9251	2. Refractive index at 30° ...	1.4554
3. Iodine value (Hanus) ...	76.0	4. Saponification value (S.V.)...	197.45
5. Reichert Meissel value...	0.53	6. Acid value ...	1.815
7. Acetyl value ...	6.0	8. Unsaponifiable matter ...	0.3%

Mixed Fatty Acids.—The oil (100 g.) was saponified with alcoholic potash. The soap was dried and extracted with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The soap was then dissolved in water and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The acids liberated were extracted with ether and worked up as usual. The mixed fatty acids, thus obtained, had the following constants : titre test, 39.0 ; equiv., 286.7 ; iodine value, 84.3 ; refractive index at 45°, 1.45648.

Separation of Solid and Liquid Acids.—The mixed fatty acids were separated into solid and liquid acids by Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method and the acids were worked up as usual. The solid acids (43.5%) and liquid acids (56.5%) had the following constants.

TABLE II

	I.V.	Equiv. wt.	M.p.
Solid acid	6.6	267.0	51-52°
Liquid acid	145.0	290.8	—

Identification of Solid Acids.—The solid acids were converted into methyl esters by Fischer Speier method. The methyl esters (35.5 g.) were fractionally distilled at 53 mm. pressure. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Fraction No.	B.p.	Wt.	Mean M.W.
I	Up to 310°	3.26 g.	—
II	310°-330°	10.0	275.3
III	330°-335	6.3	285.0
IV	335°-340°	7.9	301.6
V	340°-350°	4.39	308.3
Residue	—	1.65	—

Fraction I was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash and the resulting acids (m.p. 57-58°, equiv. wt 257.5) on crystallisation from alcohol had m.p. 60-61° and equiv. wt., 256.4. The mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of palmitic acid was unchanged. Hence this fraction consists of methyl palmitate only.

Fraction II on hydrolysis gave a mixture of acids (m.p. 60-61° and equiv. wt. 275.5). The acids were then separated by fractional precipitation with magnesium acetate when palmitic acid (m.p. 61°; equiv. wt. 256.0) and stearic acid (m.p. 68-69°; equiv. wt. 282.8) were obtained. Hence this fraction is a mixture of methyl palmitate and methyl stearate.

Fraction III was entirely methyl stearate as on hydrolysis it gave an acid (m.p. 60°; equiv. wt. 285.9). On crystallisation it had m.p. 69° and equiv. wt. 285. Mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of stearic acid was unchanged.

Fraction IV and Fraction V consisted mainly of methyl stearate and methyl behenate as on hydrolysis and fractional precipitation by magnesium acetate (5 or 6 times) it gave pure stearic acid (m.p. 69° and equiv. wt. 284) and behenic acid (m.p. 77-79°; equiv. wt. 339.6). Some of the intermediate fractions had m.p. 72-75° corresponding to that of arachidic acid but their equiv. wts. were always nearing that of behenic acid. This shows that these fractions consist mainly of methyl stearate and methyl behenate. If arachidic acid were present at all, it must be in a very small quantity.

The residue on hydrolysis and crystallisation gave an acid of m.p. 79° and equiv. wt. 339.6. Hence it must be entirely methyl behenate.

The composition of the solid acid therefore is palmitic acid, 15.86%; stearic acid, 68.53% and behenic acid, 15.63%

Identification of Liquid Acids.—The liquid acids were examined by the bromine addition method (Jamieson and Baughman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2398). The liquid acids (5 g.) were dissolved in about 50 c.c. of dry ether and bromine was added to it drop by drop till a permanent yellow colour persisted, the temperature being kept at 0-5°. Hexabromostearic acid was obtained melting at 177-78° in 0.7242 g. yield. The filtrate was washed to remove the excess of

bromine and on drying and removing the ether, the residue was dissolved in petroleum ether and kept at 0° for 2 hours. The precipitate of tetrabromostearic acid, m.p. 112-13° was obtained in a yield of 1.6886 g. The residue (6.8864 g.) was worked up as usual and its bromine content was found to be 42.97%.

The percentage of bromine in the residue is higher than that corresponding to oleic acid dibromide (36.36%). Hence it is assumed that the same weights of tetra- and hexabromostearic acids have been retained in the residue. The composition of the liquid acids therefore becomes: linolenic, 10.7%; linolic acid, 31.6%; oleic acid, 57.7%.

Assuming the weights of tetra- and hexabromostearic acids retained in the residue (6.8886) as 1.6886 g. and 0.7242 g. respectively and calculating the bromine percentage in the residue, it is found that it comes very close to that actually estimated. (Found: Br₂, 42.97. Calc., 43.5%). Hence the above assumption seems correct.

When the linolenic acid is brominated, mainly two hexabromostearic acids are formed, one being liquid and the other solid (*cf.* Hilditch, "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", Chapman and Hall, 1940, p 337). The solid hexabromostearic acid being insoluble in ether crystallises out, while the liquid isomer remains in solution. In the calculation of the composition of liquid acids, the liquid hexabromostearic acid is not generally taken into consideration. In the present work it has, however, allowed for as indicated above.

The equiv. wt. of the liquid acids (290.8) indicates that some unsaturated acid of high molecular weight may be present. Hence methyl esters of liquid acids were prepared and fractionally distilled and the high boiling fractions were analysed but they showed high equiv. wt. and varying iodine values. Hence a high molecular weight acid cannot be present. High equiv. wt. of the acid is undoubtedly due to the polymerised products of linolic and linolenic acids. (*cf.* Govindrajani, *loc. cit.*).

The composition of the mixed fatty acids is therefore palmitic acid (6.73%), stearic acid (29.12%), behenic acid (6.64%), linolenic acid (6.09%), linolic acid (18.17%) and oleic acid (33.23%).

Unsaponifiable matter.—This was obtained by the extraction of the dry soap of the oil with ether. On three crystallisations from alcohol (charcoal) it was obtained in a crystalline form, m.p. 129-30°. It gave all the colour reactions of phytosterols. The quantity of the unsaponifiable matter being very small (0.3%), its further investigation could not be carried out.